

Geometry optimization and thermodynamic stabilities of mixed ligand complexes [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂][†]

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Abstract : For the mixed ligand complexes [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] (where β -diketone = pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and L = 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanone, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)propan-1-one) computational analysis has been carried out with the help of software MOPAC 2006 using PM3 method and various parameters such as heats of formation, total energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities, atomic charges, bond lengths and bond angles have been determined. All the mixed ligand complexes are thermodynamically stable as evidenced by heats of formation. Atom electron density data suggest coordination to metal atom through oxygen atoms of the ligands. Optimized geometries have been worked out which support octahedral geometry for the complexes.

Keywords : Computational analysis, PM3 method, cobalt, β -diketones, mixed ligand complexes.

Introduction

PM3 is a semi-empirical method for the quantum mechanical calculations of molecular electronic structure to attain moderately accurate results and is based on the Neglect of Differential Diatomic Overlap Integral approximation¹. It has been extended to many elements, including transition metals and has been used to optimize the geometries of a large number of transition metal complexes²⁻⁷. Kiralj *et al.*⁸ have carried out geometry optimization of substituted benzaldehydes with the help of PM3 method. Using PM3 method Cavichiole *et al.*⁹ have proposed the structural, electronic and vibrational features of biscyanide α -iminooxime cobalt macrocyclic complex. For Co^{III} complex containing a homochiral carboxylate tetradentate ligand (*R,R*)-[(*N*-benzyl-*N*-{2-[*N*-benzyl-*N*-(pyridine-2-yl)methyl]amino}cyclohexyl)amino]acetic acid molecular calculations at PM3 level indicate that *cis*- β -*syn* is the major isomer¹⁰. Montgomery *et al.*¹¹ have investigated the mechanism of recemization and activation energies of Co(acac)₃, [Fe(phen)₃]³⁺ and Fe[S₂CN(CH₂)₄]₃ using semi-empirical PM3 method. In

the present paper we report the results of semi-empirical calculations by PM3 method using MOPAC 2006 software on [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] type of complexes, where β -diketone = pentane-2,4-dione (acetylacetone, acac), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (benzoylacetone, bzac), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (dibenzoylmethane, dbzm) and L = 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde (salicylaldehyde, sal), 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanone (hydroxyacetophenone, hap), 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)propane-1-one (hydroxypropionophenone, hpp) synthesized in our laboratories^{12,13}. Earlier we have reported computational analysis of such mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II}^{14,15}.

Results and discussion

For the mixed ligand complexes [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂], where β -diketone = pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and L = 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethanone, 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)propan-1-one (Fig. 1) computational analysis has been carried out using PM3 method and various parameters such as heats of formation, total

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Fig. 1. Structure of [Co(β-diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes.

energies, ionization potentials, atom electron densities, atomic charges, bond lengths and bond angles have been calculated.

The heat of formation of a molecule is a measure of its internal energy. The molecules with a positive heat of formation are less stable thermodynamically than the elements from which they are formed and those with negative heats of formation are more stable. For mixed ligand complexes [Co(β-diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] heats of formation are negative quantities (−431 to −354 kcal, Table 1) showing that they are more stable thermodynamically. On the basis of heats of formation the thermodynamic stabilities of the complexes are in the following order :

Total energies of the complexes range from −5319 to −3923 eV (Table 1). The ionization potentials of the mixed ligand complexes are in the range 5.83204 to 7.53469 eV (Table 1).

Atom electron densities give an idea about the coordination sites on the ligands through which the metal ions

Table 1. Heats of formation, total energies and ionization potentials for [Co(β-diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	Heats of formation (kcal)	Total energy (eV)	Ionization potential (eV)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−377.26626	−3923.13664	7.53469
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−431.55352	−4074.79653	6.25147
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−393.89395	−4222.46922	7.40870
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−384.63964	−4547.32379	5.91017
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−354.25059	−4695.31176	7.49544
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−409.48806	−4847.01285	6.49113
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	−363.86585	−5319.59613	5.83204

are bound. In the β-diketone ligands pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione, 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (Fig. 2) the atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms and carbon atom number 3 are in the range 6.1922 to

Fig. 2. Structure of β-diketones.

6.3194 and 4.3187 to 4.3292 respectively (Table 2a). These data imply that the atom electron densities on oxygen atoms are greater than those on carbon atoms which reveal that the metal ion will coordinate through oxygen rather than carbon. Most of the metals form stronger bonds with oxygen instead of carbon. Due to this, resonance stabilization is achieved in oxygen bonded complexes by the formation of the chelate ring. However, where the electronegativity of the metal is sufficiently high to reduce the affinity of metal to oxygen then the C-bonded β-diketones are formed. Atom electron densities on oxygen atoms of other ligands (Fig. 3) are in the range 6.1902 to 6.3019 (Table 2a).

In the complexes atom electron densities on the oxygen atoms surrounding cobalt are 6.3284 to 6.6178 (Table 2b), which do not differ significantly from those for the

Table 2a. Atom electron densities for ligands

Ligand	O1	O5	C2	C3	C4
Pentane-2,4-dione	6.1922	6.3180	3.6686	4.3265	3.8769
1-Phenylbutane-1,3-dione	6.2070	6.3135	3.8887	4.3187	3.6140
1,3-Diphenylpropane-1,3-dione	6.1954	6.3194	3.8192	4.3292	3.6193
2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde	6.2143	6.2978	4.2076	3.8463	4.2303
1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-ethanone	6.3019	6.1902	4.2231	3.8353	4.2046
1-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-propane-1-one	6.2996	6.1906	4.2229	3.8367	4.1998

Co-O bond lengths are in the range 1.757 to 2.213 Å (Table 4a). These bond lengths are in accord with the X-ray crystal structure data of bis(salicylidenequanylhydrazino)cobalt(III) chloride trihydrate for which Co-O bond distances have been reported to be 1.899–1.935 Å¹⁶. O-C bond distances between the oxygen atoms surrounding cobalt and the carbon atoms attached to the respective oxygen atoms are in the range 1.258 to 1.400 Å (Table 4b). The values lie between O-C (1.40 Å) and O=C (1.20 Å) suggesting delocalization of the electrons.

Table 2b. Atom electron densities for [Co(β-diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(2)	O(3)	O(4)	O(5)	O(6)	O(7)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.4200	6.5848	6.5918	6.4549	6.4215	6.3756
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.5118	6.4765	6.3884	6.3290	6.5517	6.6009
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.4073	6.6178	6.3833	6.4671	6.4682	6.5296
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.4806	6.5024	6.5881	6.5575	6.3290	6.3284
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.4244	6.5806	6.5793	6.4553	6.4309	6.3715
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.5203	6.4824	6.5908	6.5560	6.3711	6.3484
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	6.5426	6.5920	6.4279	6.5575	6.3666	6.3401

R = H, CH₃, C₂H₅

Fig. 3. Structure of other carbonyl ligands.

ligands. This may be due to the existence of similar type of ring in ligands due to hydrogen bonding. During complex formation hydrogen is merely substituted by the metal ion. Atomic charges on the oxygen atoms surrounding cobalt are –0.3284 to –0.6177 (Table 3).

Angles O(2)-Co(1)-O(7), O(3)-Co(1)-O(4) and O(5)-Co(1)-O(6) which are formed by the oxygen atoms occupying *trans* positions (Fig. 4) are close to 180° (149.278° to 176.026°) (Table 5a). Other remaining twelve O-Co-O bond angles formed by oxygen atoms occupying *cis* positions (Fig. 4) are close to 90° (67.325° to 108.874°) (Tables 5b and 5c) supporting octahedral geometry for the complexes. Chem 3D structures of [Co(acac)(hpp)(H₂O)₂], [Co(bzac)(hpp)(H₂O)₂] and [Co(dbzm)(hap)(H₂O)₂] are given in Figs. 5–7.

Thus atom electron density data calculated by semi-

Table 3. Atomic charges for [Co(β-diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(2)	O(3)	O(4)	O(5)	O(6)	O(7)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.4199	–0.5847	–0.5917	–0.4549	–0.4215	–0.3756
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.5118	–0.4764	–0.3883	–0.3290	–0.5517	–0.6009
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.4073	–0.6177	–0.3832	–0.4670	–0.4682	–0.5295
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.4805	–0.5024	–0.5880	–0.5575	–0.3289	–0.3284
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.4244	–0.5806	–0.5793	–0.4553	–0.4309	–0.3715
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.5202	–0.4824	–0.5907	–0.5560	–0.3710	–0.3484
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	–0.5426	–0.5919	–0.4278	–0.5575	–0.3665	–0.3400

Table 4a. Co-O Bond lengths for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	Co(1)-O(2)	Co(1)-O(3)	Co(1)-O(4)	Co(1)-O(5)	Co(1)-O(6)	Co(1)-O(7)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	2.033	1.792	1.860	1.757	1.955	2.044
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.994	2.043	1.953	1.935	2.061	2.211
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	2.041	1.812	1.829	1.758	1.997	1.998
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.988	2.037	1.960	1.929	2.129	2.213
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	2.035	1.792	1.845	1.761	2.042	1.964
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.998	2.029	1.958	1.944	2.076	2.200
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.943	1.939	2.066	1.975	2.206	2.091

Table 4b. C-O Bond lengths for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(2)-C(8)	O(3)-C(10)	O(4)-C(11)	O(5)-C(13)	O(6)-H(15)	O(7)-H(17)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.262	1.367	1.400	1.356	0.965	0.983
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.295	1.274	1.363	1.348	0.959	0.979
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.260	1.364	1.399	1.376	0.963	0.963
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.293	1.279	1.360	1.327	0.958	0.962
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.264	1.365	1.399	1.373	0.984	0.965
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.295	1.277	1.355	1.348	0.976	0.961
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1.356	1.349	1.318	1.258	0.960	0.960

Fig. 4. Structure of Co complex showing octahedral geometry.**Table 5a.** Bond angles for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(2)-Co(1)-	O(3)-Co(1)-	O(5)-Co(1)-
	O(7)	O(4)	O(6)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	173.655	164.999	151.105
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	173.540	168.158	172.173
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	165.808	149.278	150.860
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	176.026	171.714	174.334
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	172.930	165.488	151.351
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	173.991	166.951	171.419
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	175.247	168.788	172.173

empirical PM3 method suggest coordination to metal atom through oxygen atoms of the ligands and bond lengths and bond angles support octahedral geometry of the complexes. All the mixed ligand complexes are stable as evidenced by heats of formation data.

Methodology :

With the help of software MOPAC 2006 computational analysis has been carried out for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes using PM3 method. First the structures of the complexes are drawn in Chemdraw ultra 8.0 then MOP file is prepared by giving keywords. Then, the dos file is prepared by giving its keywords in RUN program. This dos file is run in software MOPAC 2006 and on completion, the output file containing the data of the following parameters is obtained : Heats of formation, Total energies, Ionization potentials, Atom electron densities and Atomic charges.

The MOP file is converted into PDB file through molecular structure file converter and the structures of the complexes, bond lengths and bond angles are seen in Chem 3D (Figs. 5–7).

Table 5b. Bond angles for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(2)-Co(1)-O(3)	O(2)-Co(1)-O(4)	O(2)-Co(1)-O(5)	O(2)-Co(1)-O(6)	O(3)-Co(1)-O(5)	O(3)-Co(1)-O(6)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	93.081	93.376	81.891	89.557	108.731	99.208
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	91.535	98.742	103.607	84.218	90.302	89.319
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	96.943	92.801	81.533	90.663	126.031	82.644
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	92.265	93.845	100.025	85.590	88.978	90.051
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	93.126	92.815	82.399	89.627	108.874	98.967
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	90.125	101.546	99.676	85.559	89.099	97.733
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	93.641	90.544	101.691	84.108	100.442	73.737

Table 5c. Bond angles for [Co(β -diketone)(L)(H₂O)₂] complexes

Complex	O(3)-Co(1)-O(7)	O(4)-Co(1)-O(5)	O(4)-Co(1)-O(6)	O(4)-Co(1)-O(7)	O(5)-Co(1)-O(7)	O(6)-Co(1)-O(7)
[Co(acac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	82.157	85.591	67.325	90.295	103.570	87.084
[Co(acac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	94.908	92.961	85.900	74.901	75.926	96.317
[Co(acac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	69.122	84.163	68.133	100.649	104.166	90.170
[Co(bzac)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	89.422	95.458	84.847	84.137	83.598	90.811
[Co(bzac)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	81.022	85.039	67.842	91.994	103.190	87.390
[Co(bzac)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	94.674	94.598	77.611	73.327	84.039	90.206
[Co(dbzm)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	86.574	88.863	96.393	88.402	82.925	91.403

Fig. 5. 3D structure of [Co(acac)(hpp)(H₂O)₂] complex.

Fig. 6. 3D structure of $[\text{Co}(\text{bzac})(\text{hpp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex.

Fig. 7. 3D structure of $[\text{Co}(\text{dbzm})(\text{hap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ complex.

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